

The Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace: contextualising digital resources in a registry

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The Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace (SSH Open Marketplace) - marketplace.sshopencloud.eu - is a discovery portal which pools and contextualises resources for Social Sciences and Humanities research communities: tools, services, training materials, datasets, publications and workflows. The SSH Open Marketplace showcases solutions and research practices for every step of the research data life cycle. In doing so, it facilitates discoverability and findability of research services and products that are essential to enable sharing and re-use of workflows and methodologies.

Initiated in the Digital Humanities (DH) context, inspired by the DiRT directory (Dombrowski 2014), TAPoR¹ or the Standardization Survival Kit (Riondet et al. 2018) and aggregating their data for its initial population, the SSH Open Marketplace was built as part of the SSHOC project². Acting as a thematic entry door into the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)³, this discovery service is now funded and maintained by three European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERIC) - DARIAH⁴, CLARIN⁵ and CESSDA⁶ - as part of the SSH Open Cluster. The collaboration between the SSH Open Marketplace stakeholders (funders, providers, moderators or contributors) ensures that the cataloguing and contextualising efforts are meaningful and undertaken by and serve DH researchers.

Based on the idea that DH tool registries should be community led and trying to take into consideration the limits highlighted for similar projects, under the “directory paradox” concept (Dombrowski 2021), the SSH Open Marketplace can count on an Editorial Board, composed of 17 members, to ensure the day-to-day maintenance and the data quality of the SSH Open Marketplace.

Liaising with the service providers and the end-users of the service (SSH researchers and support staff for researchers), the Editorial Board ensures the technical running of operation, the effectiveness of the curation process and the editorial policy's successful implementation.

With a population of ~6000 items, aggregated from 15+ trusted sources, the SSH Open Marketplace relies on community curation - i.e. contributions from the research communities in SSH and from the Editorial Board - to ensure the catalogue entries remain up-to-date and useful for SSH researchers, the end-users of the portal. Furthermore, curation routines, mixing automatic and manual tasks are set up to ensure and continuously improve (meta)data quality.

How can the SSH Open Marketplace help DH researchers? Thanks to this service, researchers can gain access to useful and well curated resources and find and discover digital tools and methods. Because contextualisation is provided between the items of the catalogue, it is easy to understand and assess the usefulness of a resource. Furthermore, the SSH Open Marketplace is also an ideal place to promote researchers' work, e.g. by adding information about the tool or workflow they develop.

This poster presents how the SSH Open Marketplace can provide insights into the use of tools, methods and standards in the DH research communities, and how it can increase serendipity in the discovery of new methods and standards, by interlinking the resources and describing workflows. Participants of the Digital Humanities Conference 2023 are invited to contribute to the creation of new or enrichment of existing records, as getting involved in these data curation routines is also an opportunity to be actively involved in the DH community.

Notes

1. TAPoR 3: <https://tapor.ca/>. The Text Analysis Portal for Research is a project led by Geoffrey Rockwell and Milena Radzikowska.
2. See <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/823782>
3. See <https://eosc.eu/about-eosc>
4. The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities: <https://www.dariah.eu>
5. The Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure: <https://www.clarin.eu>
6. The Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives: <https://www.cessda.eu>

Bibliography

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